

A Review of Revolutionizing Document Verification: A Comprehensive Exploration of Polygon Mainnet's Superiority Over Traditional Systems

Diksha Konale

Department of Computer

Science and Engineering

Nutan College of

Engineering and Research

Pune, India

Baibhav Saini

Department of Computer

Science and Engineering,

Nutan College of

Engineering and Research

Pune, India

Nayana Ghatol

Department of Computer

Science and Engineering

Nutan College of

Engineering and Research

Pune, India

Jaydeep Adik

Department of Computer

Science and Engineering

Nutan College of

Engineering and Research

Pune, India

Prof. Dipamala Chaudhari

Department of Computer Science and Engineering,

Nutan College of Engineering and Research

Pune, India

Abstract—The rapid growth of information technology and the ready availability of advanced office instruments have intensified concerns about the forgery of crucial documents. This escalating threat necessitates robust verification and authentication practices for various vital documents, including banking records, government papers, transaction documents, and educational certificates. Unfortunately, existing document verification processes are often intricate and time-consuming, prompting the exploration of more efficient solutions.

In response to these challenges, this research introduces a decentralized web application designed for digital document verification, leveraging the Ethereum blockchain. The application utilizes peer-to-peer (P2P) cloud storage to enhance the verification process, fostering openness, transparency, and auditability.

Moreover, each uploaded document is assigned a unique hash value, adding an additional layer of security and traceability. Our model effectively addresses the shortcomings and complexities inherent in traditional document verification methods, providing a comprehensive solution that aligns with the requirements of a digital document verification system. Through the incorporation of blockchain technology, our proposed model not only streamlines the

verification process but also establishes a secure and tamper-proof framework, ensuring the integrity of important documents in an increasingly digitalized world.

Keywords: Public/private key cryptography, Digital signatures, Hash functions, Proof of work, Transparency, Auditability, Tamper-proof, Information technology, Decentralized web application.

I. INTRODUCTION

The state of roads has a substantial influence on both safety and security. The ever-increasing speed of information exchange is propelling both businesses and individuals toward the adoption of digitized documents. The cumbersome and time-consuming nature of handling traditional physical documents is driving users to seek modern, efficient methods for issuing and validating essential documents. Despite the undeniable convenience of digital documents, ensuring their authenticity remains a significant challenge. The technological revolution, along with easy access to sophisticated equipment, has made it easier to forge important documents, presenting a substantial threat to document authenticity. The severe consequences of fraudulent documentation demand immediate attention. Consequently, a robust system for validating the authenticity of critical documents is indispensable for users aiming to

maintain the integrity of their digital records. Blockchain, with its open-source, immutable, and consensus-driven model, offers a promising solution to this pressing issue.

Blockchain technology, a relatively recent innovation, has the potential to significantly enhance document verification processes and effectively combat document fraud and misuse. Essentially, blockchain functions as a distributed database that chronologically stores blocks, each containing data packs or documents, making it virtually impossible to alter these records. The advanced features of blockchain, such as trust, integrity, consensus, autonomy, and security, make it an attractive technology for various industries, including document verification. Inspired by the reliability, transparency, and incorruptibility of blockchain technology, our work incorporates Ethereum blockchain to authenticate important digital documents.

As we embark on this review paper, our primary objective is to explore the limitations of traditional document verification systems, particularly those using Ethereum blockchain technology, and propose an innovative approach utilizing Polygon Mainnet. Document forgery remains a significant challenge, and existing verification systems often fail to ensure both availability and content integrity.

In contrast to Ethereum, Polygon Mainnet offers a compelling solution to prevalent issues in document verification. The use of stable and widely extended public blockchains, such as Polygon Mainnet, has the potential to revolutionize the verification of official documents, ensuring trustworthiness and cost-effectiveness. The subsequent sections will delve into the intricacies of implementing Polygon Mainnet in our proposed system and highlight its efficiency compared to Ethereum, offering a comprehensive analysis of the potential benefits in revolutionizing document verification processes.

Fig. Document Verification Process.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Document verification has become a critical aspect across various sectors, ensuring authenticity and integrity in records and certificates. This literature review aims to comprehensively examine existing methods in blockchain-based document verification systems, analyzing their strengths, weaknesses, and anticipated challenges. As document fraud remains a significant concern, advancements in blockchain technology offer promising solutions to enhance security and transparency. Consequently, exploring novel approaches such as decentralized verification protocols and integration with emerging blockchain platforms is essential for addressing current limitations and paving the way for more robust verification mechanisms.

1. Evolution of Document Verification Methods

Assessing Automated Methods for Document Verification

Document verification methodologies have evolved significantly with the introduction of advanced technological solutions. This section compares three prominent approaches: blockchain-based verification, cryptographic techniques, and decentralized validation protocols.

1.1 Blockchain-based verification:

Blockchain-based verification leverages blockchain technology, originally introduced through cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, as a decentralized and distributed ledger system. This approach revolutionizes document verification by offering a transparent and tamper-proof method without the need for a central authority. Key features include decentralization, where data is stored across a network of computers (nodes), enhancing security by eliminating single points of failure. Immutability ensures that once data is recorded on the blockchain, it cannot be altered retroactively without consensus from the majority of the network, thereby guaranteeing data integrity. Transparency is another critical aspect, as all transactions and changes are visible to all participants, fostering trust and enabling auditability.

In the context of document verification, blockchain-based systems store unique digital fingerprints of documents called hashes on the blockchain. These hashes serve as cryptographic proofs of document authenticity. When verification is required,

the document's hash is compared against the hash stored on the blockchain. If they match, the document is verified as authentic. Platforms like Ethereum and Hyperledger provide robust frameworks for developing blockchain-based verification systems, widely applied in sectors such as supply chain management, healthcare records, and academic credentials verification. This technology not only enhances security and reliability but also streamlines processes by reducing reliance on traditional, centralized verification methods.

1.2 Cryptographic Techniques:

Cryptographic techniques are essential in modern document verification methodologies due to their ability to ensure data security, authenticity, and integrity. These techniques leverage mathematical algorithms and keys to protect sensitive information and verify the validity of documents in digital environments. Symmetric encryption algorithms like AES ensure confidentiality by using a single shared key for encryption and decryption. Asymmetric encryption algorithms such as RSA facilitate secure communication and authentication by employing a pair of keys: a public key for encryption and a private key for decryption. Hash functions like SHA-256 generate unique digital fingerprints (hashes) for documents, enabling verification of data integrity and detecting tampering. Key Derivation Functions (KDFs) enhance security by deriving encryption keys from passwords or passphrases securely. Digital signatures provide cryptographic proof of document authenticity and origin, ensuring non-repudiation in electronic transactions. Together, these cryptographic techniques support secure transmission, storage, and verification of documents across various sectors, including finance, healthcare, and legal industries.

1.2.1. Symmetric Encryption Algorithms:

Symmetric encryption algorithms play a crucial role in data security by utilizing a single key for both encrypting and decrypting information. This shared key is used by both the sender and receiver, ensuring that only authorized parties can access the encrypted data. One of the most prominent examples of symmetric encryption algorithms is the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES), renowned for its robust security and efficiency. AES supports key sizes of 128, 192, or 256 bits, making it adaptable to different security requirements across

various applications. Its widespread adoption stems from its capability to securely transmit sensitive data over networks and protect stored data on devices and servers from unauthorized access or tampering. By employing symmetric encryption, organizations can maintain confidentiality in communication channels and safeguard data integrity at rest, bolstering overall cybersecurity measures effectively.

1.2.2. Asymmetric Encryption Algorithms:

Asymmetric encryption algorithms are pivotal in modern cryptography, employing a pair of keys to enhance security through distinct roles: a public key for encryption and a private key for decryption. These keys are mathematically linked but cannot be derived from one another, ensuring robust protection against unauthorized access. A prominent example of an asymmetric encryption algorithm is RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman), renowned for its versatility in securing digital signatures, facilitating key exchange, and enabling secure communication over insecure networks. RSA operates within Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) systems, where it plays a critical role in ensuring secure communication channels, managing cryptographic keys, and authenticating entities. By utilizing asymmetric encryption, organizations can establish trust in digital transactions, safeguard sensitive information during transmission, and uphold the integrity of data exchanges, bolstering overall cybersecurity frameworks effectively.

1.2.3. Hash Function:

Hash functions play a fundamental role in cryptography by transforming input data, whether it's a message, file, or any digital information, into a fixed-size string of characters known as a hash value or digest. This transformation is deterministic, ensuring that the same input always results in the same hash output. One of the widely used cryptographic hash functions is SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm 256-bit), which generates a 256-bit (32-byte) hash value.

These hash functions find crucial applications across various domains. They are integral in verifying data integrity, where comparing hash values ensures that data has not been altered or corrupted. Hash functions are also employed in secure password storage practices, where passwords are hashed and stored as hash values instead of plaintext to enhance security. In digital signatures, hashing is employed before signing to ensure

the integrity of the signed content. Moreover, hash functions are pivotal in blockchain technology, where each block in the blockchain is hashed to maintain the integrity and immutability of the entire chain. Thus, hash functions serve as essential cryptographic tools enabling secure data transmission, authentication, and integrity verification in modern digital environments.

1.2.4. Key Derivation Functions (KDF):

Key Derivation Functions (KDFs) are cryptographic mechanisms designed to derive one or more cryptographic keys from a source key material, such as a password or passphrase. The primary purpose of KDFs is to securely generate keys that can be used for encryption, decryption, or other cryptographic operations. Common examples of KDFs include PBKDF2 (Password-Based Key Derivation Function 2) and bcrypt. PBKDF2, for instance, iteratively applies a pseudorandom function to derive a key from a password, enhancing security by making brute-force attacks more difficult. KDFs are crucial in scenarios where keys need to be securely derived from user-provided passwords or passphrases, thereby enhancing the security of stored data and communication channels.

1.2.5. Digital Signatures:

Digital signatures are cryptographic techniques used to provide authenticity and integrity assurance for digital messages or documents. A digital signature allows a recipient to verify that a document was indeed created by a specific sender and has not been altered since it was signed. This is achieved through mathematical algorithms that generate a unique digital fingerprint, or signature, for each document. Common algorithms used in digital signatures include RSA with the Digital Signature Algorithm (DSA) and Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA). Digital signatures are essential for document authentication, ensuring non-repudiation (preventing the signer from denying their involvement), and maintaining data integrity in electronic transactions and contracts. They play a critical role in verifying the identity of parties involved in digital communications and transactions, thereby establishing trust and reliability in electronic exchanges.

2. Document Verification Methodologies

This section explores recent advancements and methodologies in document verification, showcasing innovative applications of blockchain technology and cryptographic techniques.

2.1 DOC-BLOCK: Decentralized Document Verification

[1] Iftekher Toufique Imam, Yamin Arafat, Kazi Saeed Alam, and Shaikh Akib Shahriyar from Khulna University of Engineering & Technology present "DOC-BLOCK," a decentralized web application leveraging Ethereum blockchain. Their system enhances the verification process for critical documents such as banking records, government certificates, and educational credentials. By employing public/private key cryptography, online storage security, digital signatures, and hash functions, DOC-BLOCK ensures transparent and auditable document verification. Key features include document storage, verification, and download functionalities, addressing challenges in traditional verification processes and offering heightened security and efficiency.

2.2 Blockchain-Based System for Educational Records

[2] Prof. A. D. Londhe and team propose a blockchain-based system designed to combat document forgery, particularly in educational records. This system creates electronic counterparts of paper documents stored on a blockchain, ensuring tamper-proof integrity and reducing the risk of document loss. The technology incorporates Polygon Mainnet for enhanced efficiency, generating QR codes for streamlined online verification. With applications in education and scientific research, this system aims to revolutionize document validation by leveraging blockchain's transparency and security benefits.

2.3 Digital Certificate Verification Using Blockchain

[3] Khushal Y. Bheke and team present a system for digital certificate verification using blockchain technology, emphasizing the prevention of fake certificates. Their approach utilizes smart contracts, SHA256 hash generation, and mining algorithms to create secure and unmodifiable digital certificates. This system aims to reduce costs, prevent forgery, and provide reliable information through robust cryptographic mechanisms. By enhancing certificate verification processes, the research

underscores the transformative potential of blockchain in ensuring document authenticity and integrity.

2.4 Blockchain-Based Certificate Verification and Transcript Generation

[4] Ravi Singh Lamkoti and team propose a blockchain-based solution for certificate verification and transcript generation using Ethereum blockchain and IPFS. The system involves Certificate Issuers securely storing certificates on IPFS with corresponding hashes on the Ethereum blockchain. Students access certificates using unique IDs, while Validators verify documents through ID entry or document upload. This approach enhances efficiency, security, and reliability in the document verification process, showcasing blockchain's capability in education sector applications.

2.5 Document Verification System using Blockchain and IPFS

[5] Zainuddin and Choo propose a document verification system integrating Ethereum blockchain, Truffle Suite, IPFS Cluster, and AES encryption. This system enhances security and efficiency by storing IPFS hash values on Ethereum, ensuring content integrity and controlled access. The research addresses limitations in existing systems, emphasizing the development of a robust blockchain-based solution for document verification. By employing advanced cryptographic techniques, the system aims to provide secure file storage and verification capabilities, contributing to improved document authenticity and trustworthiness.

2.6 Secure Online Document Verification using Blockchain

[6] Abhijeet Gupta and team propose a secure online document verification system leveraging blockchain technology. Their approach ensures document authenticity by creating tamper-proof digital fingerprints stored on a blockchain. The system architecture and methodology emphasize decentralization and transparency, addressing fraud concerns in document verification processes across multiple sectors including identity, education, healthcare, legal, and financial services. The research highlights blockchain's potential in transforming traditional document

verification methods to enhance security and reliability.

[7] The paper by K. N. Pankov from Moscow Technical University focuses on enhancing the quality of software for distributed ledger systems in the transport industry using blockchain technology. It discusses the challenges of safety and security in blockchain implementation, emphasizing testing, verification, and validation. The author identifies existing tools, especially in the aviation sector, and highlights the need for standardized norms. The research proposes adding testing technologies to the roadmap and explores the concepts of testing, verification, and validation in software development. The article concludes by stressing the importance of universal testing tools for evolving distributed ledger systems.

[8] Paper published in the Journal of Physics: Conference Series, Aisong Zhang and Xinxin Ma propose a decentralized digital certificate revocation system based on blockchain. The system utilizes consortium blockchain and a secret sharing scheme to enhance trust, stability, and synchronization among multiple certification authorities. It aims to protect user information and property security by invalidating digital certificates in specific cases. The scheme introduces a penalty mechanism and blacklist to handle uncooperative authorities, ensuring the reliability and security of the revocation process. The authors highlight the potential of their approach in providing a trusted and reliable system for digital certificate revocation across multiple authorities, expanding the application of blockchain.

[9] Vivek Madala, Mahavir Prasad Jhanwar, and Anupam Chattopadhyay propose CTB (Certificate Transparency using Blockchain) to enhance SSL/TLS security. CTB, implemented on IBM's Hyperledger Fabric, prevents CAs from issuing certificates without domain owner consent, ensuring transparency and accountability. The system includes a certificate revocation mechanism and seamlessly integrates with the existing X.509 PKI-based SSL/TLS. The authors emphasize CTB's flexibility, efficiency, and security features compared to Google's Certificate Transparency.

[10] Wang, Lin, and team propose using Polygon Mainnet as an alternative to Ethereum for document verification. They highlight the drawbacks of traditional systems and emphasize

the benefits of blockchain, particularly in education and scientific research. Their decentralized web application, leveraging smart contracts, aims to enhance transparency and security in document verification processes, offering potential solutions to challenges faced by existing systems. The authors also discuss specific applications, such as streamlining certificate validation in the Indian education system. Overall, the research explores the advantages of Polygon Mainnet in revolutionizing document verification across industries.

[11] In IEEE ICASI 2018 paper, Jiin-Chiou Cheng and team propose a blockchain-based system to address the prevalent issue of certificate forgery, focusing on educational certificates in Taiwan. They leverage blockchain's unmodifiable properties to create digital certificates with anti-counterfeit features. The system involves generating electronic files, calculating hash values, and storing them in the blockchain. The use of Ethereum enhances security. The proposed system ensures data accuracy, reduces certificate forgery risks, and offers a reliable platform for certificate management.

[12] In the paper, "Certificate Verification and Validation Using Blockchain," the authors propose a solution to the challenges of certificate forgery and verification. They suggest storing certificates in the Blockchain system to enhance security and use a mobile application for swift and efficient verification. The proposed system addresses the issues of document fraud and aims to improve the overall security and integrity of digital certificates.

[13] Gayathiri et al. present a solution to the challenges of certificate forgery by leveraging blockchain technology. The authors focus on the digitalization of SSLC, HSC, and academic certificates in educational institutions. Recognizing the difficulty students face in maintaining physical certificates, the project aims to provide a secure storage solution within the blockchain system. The process involves converting paper certificates into digital ones, utilizing a chaotic algorithm for hash code generation, and storing these certificates in the blockchain. The validation of certificates is facilitated through a mobile application, ensuring a more secure and efficient digital certificate verification process. The proposed system addresses the issues of document tampering and provides enhanced

security, validity, and confidentiality for graduation certificates. The paper contributes to the evolving landscape of certificate verification systems by incorporating blockchain technology to combat fraudulent practices.

III.CONCLUSION

3.1 Conclusions and Future Directions

The research surveys discussed various methodologies and technologies that advance the field of document verification and validation. Each approach demonstrated unique strengths and limitations, paving the way for further developments in this critical area.

Insights from Blockchain-Based Verification

Studies like those by Iftekher Toufique Imam et al., Prof. A. D. Londhe and team, and Khushal Y. Bheke et al. highlight the efficacy of blockchain technology in enhancing document verification. These systems leverage cryptographic techniques, digital signatures, and decentralized storage to ensure transparency and security. However, challenges such as scalability and integration with existing systems require continued exploration and refinement.

Strengths and Limitations of Asymmetric Encryption

Asymmetric encryption, exemplified by RSA and ECDSA, offers robust solutions for secure communication and digital signatures. Its reliance on public/private key pairs enhances data integrity and authentication. Yet, computational overhead and key management complexities necessitate ongoing optimization and practical implementation strategies.

Precision in Hash Functions

Hash functions like SHA-256 provide essential tools for data integrity verification and password storage. Their deterministic output ensures consistent verification of document authenticity. However, vulnerabilities in collision resistance and the need for continuous algorithmic improvements underscore areas for future research and standardization efforts.

3.2 Future Directions

Integration of Advanced Cryptographic Techniques

Future research should explore hybrid approaches that combine blockchain-based verification with advanced cryptographic techniques. This integration could mitigate current limitations and enhance the overall security and efficiency of document verification systems.

Real-Time Implementation and Scalability

Efforts should focus on implementing real-time document verification capabilities. Building on existing frameworks like those proposed by Abhijeet Gupta et al. and Zainuddin and Choo, advancements in edge computing and blockchain scalability are crucial for widespread adoption and usability.

Resilience in Challenging Environments

Enhancing the resilience of verification algorithms in diverse environments, including low-bandwidth settings and variable lighting conditions, is essential. Expanded datasets encompassing diverse document types and environmental factors will bolster algorithmic robustness and reliability.

Collaboration Across Disciplines

Collaborative efforts between cybersecurity experts, blockchain developers, and industry stakeholders are vital for developing practical and effective document verification solutions. Integrating domain-specific insights with technical expertise will yield more sophisticated and deployable verification systems.

3.3 Final Thoughts

The reviewed surveys underscore significant progress in document verification methodologies, emphasizing enhanced security and reliability in digital transactions. Each approach showcases distinct benefits and challenges, indicating opportunities for refinement and innovation in the field. Moving forward, the convergence of blockchain-based verification,

cryptographic techniques, and decentralized protocols holds promise for revolutionizing document integrity assurance. Realizing the full potential of these technologies requires a concerted focus on scalability, real-time applicability, and resilience against evolving threats. Collaboration across disciplines—combining expertise in cybersecurity, blockchain development, and regulatory frameworks—is crucial for advancing robust and adaptable document verification systems that meet the needs of modern digital ecosystems.

REFERENCES

1. A. Husain, "Printed Document Integrity Verification Using Barcode," *Jurnal Teknologi (Sciences & Engineering)*, vol. 70:1, p. 99–106, 2014.
2. B. Thuraisingham, "Blockchain Technologies and Their Applications in Data Science and Cyber Security," in *2020 3rd International Conference on Smart BlockChain (SmartBlock)*, Texas, 2020.
3. J. Jayachitra, Dr. S. Matilda, A. Gayathiri, "Certificate validation using blockchain," in *2020 7th International Conference on Smart Structures and Systems (ICSSS)*, Villupuram, 2020.
4. Barbara Guidi, Andrea Michienzi, Laura Ricci, "Data Persistence in Decentralized Social Applications: The IPFS approach," in *2021 IEEE 18th Annual Consumer Communications & Networking Conference (CCNC)*, Italy, 2021.
5. Emmanuel Nyaletey, Reza M. Parizi, Qi Zhang, Kim-Kwang Raymond Choo, "BlockIPFS - Blockchain-Enabled Interplanetary File System for Forensic and Trusted Data Traceability," in *2019 IEEE International Conference on Blockchain (Blockchain)*, USA, 2019.
6. Alexander Von Tottleben, Cornelius Ihle, Moritz Schubotz, Bela Gipp, "Academic Storage Cluster," in *2021 ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries (JCDL)*, Germany, 2021.
7. IBM, "What is blockchain technology?" IBM, [Online]. Available: <https://www.ibm.com/myen/topics/what-is-blockchain>.
8. Ivan, "InterPlanetary File System Explained – What is IPFS?"

- Moralis Academy, 8 April 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://academy.moralis.io/blog/interplanetary-file-system-explained-what-is-ipfs>.
9. S. Adhami, G. Giudici, and S. Martinazzi, "Why do businesses go crypto? An empirical analysis of initial coin offerings", *Journal of Economics and Business*, Vol. 100, No. 1, pp. 64–75, 2018.
 10. M. Nofer, P. Gomber, O. Hinz, and D. Schiereck, "Blockchain", *Business and Information Systems Engineering*, Vol. 59, No. 3, pp. 183–187, 2017.
 11. D. Drescher, *Blockchain Basics: A NonTechnical Introduction in 25 Steps*, Vol. 276, Apress, New York, N.Y.2017.
 12. V. Gatteschi, F. Lamberti, C. Demartini, C. Pranteda, and V. Santamaria, "To Blockchain or Not to Blockchain: That Is the Question", *IT Professional*, Vol. 20, No. 2, pp. 62–74, 2018.
 13. M. D. Pierro, "What Is the Blockchain?", *Computing in Science and Engineering*, Vol. 19, No. 5, pp. 92–95, 2017.
 14. A. Markelevich, "What is Blockchain Technology", *Accounting Education News*, Vol. 46, No. 4, pp. 20-21, 2018.
 15. M. Alshahrani, N. Beloff, and M. White, "Revolutionising Higher Education by Adopting Blockchain Technology in the Certification Process", In: *Proc. of Internation Conf. On Innovation and Intelligence for Informatics, Computing and Technologies*, Sakheer, Bahrain, pp. 1-6, 2020.
 16. V. Badhe, P. Nhavale, S. Todkar, P. Shinde, and K. Kolhar, "Digital Certificate System for Verification of Educational Certificates using Blockchain", *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, Vol. 7, No. 5, pp. 45–50, 2020.
 17. M. G. Aguilar, J. M. D. Fuentes, L. G. Manzano, and D. Arroyo, "Achieving Cybersecurity in Blockchain-Based Systems: A Survey", *Future Generation Computer Systems*, Vol. 124, No. 6, pp. 91–118, 2021.
 18. M. Saad, J. Spaulding, L. Njilla, C. Kamhoua, S. Shetty, D. H. Nyang, and D. Mohaisen, "Exploring the Attack Surface of Blockchain: A Comprehensive Survey", *IEEE Communications Surveys and Tutorials*, Vol. 22, No. 3, pp. 1977–2008, 2020.
 19. Z. Xu and C. Zou, "What can blockchain do and cannot do?", *China Economic Journal*, Vol. 14, o. 1, pp. 4–25, 2021.
 20. A. Karale and H. Khanuja, "Blockchain Technology in Education System: A Review", *International Journal of Computer Applications*, Vol. 178, No. 38, pp. 19-22, 2019.
 21. T. Arndt and A. Guercio, "Blockchain-based Transcripts for Mobile Higher-Education", *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, Vol. 10, No. 2, pp. 84–89, 2020.
 22. W. Gräther, S. Kolvenbach, R. Ruland, J. Schütte, C. Torres, and F. Wendland, "Blockchain for Education: Lifelong Learning Passport", In: W. Prinz & P. Hoschka (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st ERCIM Blockchain Workshop 2018*, Reports of the European Society for Socially Embedded Technologies, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 2018.
 23. M. Turkanović, M. Hölbl, K. Košič, M. Heričko, and A. Kamišalić, "EduCTX: A BlockchainBased Higher Education Credit Platform"